

Performance assessment of Tsunami-HySEA model for NTHMP tsunami currents benchmarking. II Field data

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Abstract. In this study, we present model results derived from the tsunami current benchmarking workshop held by the NTHMP (National Tsunami Hazard Mitigation Program) at Portland in February 2015 for the two benchmark problems dealing with field data. In this workshop, the Tsunami-HySEA model was used to perform the five numerical benchmarks proposed. The three benchmarks based on lab data are the subject of a companion paper (part I). The results and comparison with measured data for the two benchmarks dealing with field observations are described in the present paper, this includes: (1) Benchmark #2, impact of tsunami waves at Hilo Harbor, Hawaii, and (2) Benchmark #3, tsunami currents at Tauranga Harbor, New Zealand, both for data from the 2011 Tohoku event. We demonstrate that the Tsunami-HySEA model is able to accurately reproducing sea surface elevations and current velocities for both the local reduced benchmark problem as in the case of the complete scenario modeled from the source.

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1 Introduction

The tsunami modeling community has focused most of its effort in modeling wave height and runup as the key ingredients for tsunami hazard assessment, and model validation has been mostly restricted to these variables (Nicolosky et al. 2011; NTHMP 2012 and references therein; Tolkova 2014; Horrillo et al. 2015, and many others). In the other hand, studies focused in modeling the effects of tsunami currents or devoted to model validation for tsunami currents are less common (Lynett et al. 2014). Nevertheless, the impact cause by strong currents which typically accompany a tsunami is of key importance in ports, bays and harbors, or even in the streets between buildings for larger tsunamis (as the case of Onawaka during the 2011 Tohoku tsunami). The ability to compute and predict tsunami flow velocities has revealed of importance in risk assessment and hazard mitigation. Model results are increasingly

being used to estimate damage to coastal infrastructure, therefore understanding the accuracy and precision of speed predictions becomes of undeniable importance. Nevertheless, until recently, a benchmarking based on velocity current observations was difficult to perform as few direct measurements of tsunami velocities existed to compare with model results. Since 2011 Tohoku, this changed as many current meters were deployed in several locations around the Pacific.

Aware of this need for validation and verification, and also aware of the lack of model benchmarking for tsunami currents, the National Tsunami Hazard Mitigation Program (NTHMP) decided to implement a benchmarking procedure to evaluate NTHMP certified models for current predictions. The previous benchmark tests mandated by the NTHMP focused in wave height and runup (NTHMP 2012). To fulfill this new mandate a benchmarking workshop was organized in February, 2015 in Portland, Oregon (http://coastal.usc.edu/currents_workshop/), “*NTHMP/MMS Benchmarking Workshop: Tsunami currents*”. For this workshop, five different benchmark problems were proposed, including laboratory datasets and observed data. The two first benchmark problems were mandatory for all participating modelers/models, with the remainder of the tests being optional. Benchmarks #1, #4, and #5 were based on lab measure data, and are the subject of a companion paper (Macías et al. 2017a). BP#2 proposed the simulation of a field case for the Hilo Harbor during the 2011 Tohoku event. The third test dealt with the impact of 2011 Tohoku tsunami on Tauranga Harbor, New Zealand, whose aim was to include the effects of tides. The Tsunami-HySEA model from the University of Malaga participated in the workshop and presented numerical results for all the five benchmark problems proposed. As output of the workshop, a model inter-comparison study it is being elaborated (Lynett et al. 2017, to appear) and a report containing all model results was produced (NTHMP, 2016). In the present work, we include a summary of the numerical results obtained with the Tsunami-HySEA model for the two benchmark problems based on field data.

This paper is outlined as follows. Section 2 describes the numerical model: equations and numerical aspects. Sections 4 and 5 describe the two benchmark problems and present the numerical results obtained with the Tsunami-HySEA model, for Hilo Harbor and Tauranga Harbor, respectively. Section 6 concludes the paper with some final comments and remarks.

2 The Tsunami-HySEA numerical model

The open source Tsunami-HySEA model (edanya.uma.es/hysea/) was used to perform the numerical simulations for the two benchmark problems considered in this work and based on field data, different scenarios were simulated for both benchmarks. The Tsunami-HySEA numerical model combines robustness, reliability and good accuracy in a model based on a GPU faster than real time (FTRT) implementation. It has been severely tested, and, in particular, has passed all tests in Synolakis et al. (2008), but also other laboratory tests and proposed benchmark problems. Tsunami-HySEA has recently been approved (February 2017) by NTHMP for propagation and inundation studies in the USA. The numerical results submitted to MMS/NTHMP for obtaining this approval can be found in Macías et al (2017b). A comparison of Tsunami-HySEA numerical results with the MOST model for LANTEX 2013 scenario and tsunami impact on Puerto Rico coasts can be found in Macías et al. (2016).

Tsunami-HySEA implements the well-known 2D nonlinear one-layer shallow water system in both spherical and Cartesian coordinates. For the sake of brevity and simplicity, only the latter system is written:

$$\begin{aligned} h_t + (q_x)_x + (q_y)_y &= 0 \\ (q_x)_t + (q_x^2/h + g h^2/2)_x + (q_x q_y/h)_y &= ghH_x + S_x \\ (q_y)_t + (q_x q_y/h)_x + (q_y^2/h + g h^2/2)_y &= ghH_y + S_y \end{aligned}$$

In the previous set of equations, $h(\mathbf{x}, t)$, denotes the thickness of the water layer at point $\mathbf{x} \in D \subset R^2$ at time t , being D the horizontal projection of the 3D domain where the tsunami takes place. $H(\mathbf{x})$ is the depth of the bottom at point \mathbf{x} measured from a fixed level of reference. Let us also define the function $\eta(\mathbf{x}, t) = h(\mathbf{x}, t) - H(\mathbf{x})$ that corresponds to the free surface of the fluid. Let us denote by $q(\mathbf{x}, t) = (q_x(\mathbf{x}, t), q_y(\mathbf{x}, t))$ the mass-flow of the water layer at point \mathbf{x} at time t . The mass-flow is related to the height-averaged velocity $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ by means of the expression $q(\mathbf{x}, t) = h(\mathbf{x}, t) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. The notation $(\cdot)_t$, $(\cdot)_x$ and $(\cdot)_y$ applies for temporal and spatial partial derivatives in the x and y directions, respectively.

The terms S_x and S_y parameterize the friction effects and two different laws are considered:

- The Manning law:

$$\begin{aligned} S_x &= -gh M_n^2 u_x \|u\| / h^{4/3} \\ S_y &= -gh M_n^2 u_y \|u\| / h^{4/3} \end{aligned}$$

where $M_n > 0$ is the manning coefficient.

- A quadratic law

$$\begin{aligned} S_x &= -c_f u_x \|u\| \\ S_y &= -c_f u_y \|u\| \end{aligned}$$

where $c_f > 0$ is the friction coefficient.

For further details on the numerical method implemented in the Tsunami-HySEA model refers to the companion paper (Macías et al 2017a). The numerical implementation of Tsunami-HySEA has been performed on GPU clusters (de la Asunción et al 2011; de la Asunción et al 2013; Castro et al. 2011) and also includes nested-grids (Macías et al. 2016; Macías et al. 2017b, Macías and Ortega 2017). The benchmark problems, as initially devised for the Portland NTHMP Benchmarking Workshop, were described as “reduced scenarios”, with the “source” described as a sea surface elevation time series to be imposed close to the coast. Nevertheless, also “complete scenario” simulations, from the source, were encouraged. We performed both the reduce and the complete scenario simulations and compare model results with observations in both cases. For the complete scenarios, nested grids were used. The GPU and multi-GPU implementation and the use of nested grids allow to speed-up the computations, being able to perform complex simulations, in very large domains, much faster than real time (Macías et al. 2016, Macías et al. 2017b). In this work, we will present the figures for the wall clock time required for these simulations.

3. Benchmark Problem #2: Tsunami Currents in Hilo Harbor

The 2011 Tohoku tsunami caused persistent oscillations and hazardous currents in coastal waters around Hawaii that resulted in damage in harbors and marinas. At the same time, extensive current measurements were collected during

this event in and around Hawaii, and estimates of tsunami-induced currents were extracted from these measurements via spectral analysis (Cheung et al. 2013; Arcos and LeVeque 2015). The present benchmark test focuses on a smaller region around Hilo Harbor, and conduct a model convergence test with respect to grid resolution. The main goal was to assess the model’s ability to simulate field-scale tsunami currents under realistic grid resolutions used previously for tsunami propagation and inundation.

The aim of this benchmark focuses on understanding the importance of model resolution and numerics on prediction of tsunami currents. In order to fulfil this objective some questions were proposed to modelers to be answered (Lynett et al 2017):

1. What level of precision can we expect with regard to the simulated currents on real bathymetry?
2. Does your model converge with respect to speed predictions as resolution is increased?
3. What is the variation across different models, using the same wave forcing, resolution and bottom friction?
(to answer this question was one of the main issues of this benchmark test in the inter-comparison exercise)

In order to get a most clear answer to these questions, this field case was simplified providing a flattened bathymetry for depths larger than 30 m. This seems to contradict aim of question 1) above, but was done with the aim of model results were as similar as possible outside the protected harbor and that inter-model differences resulted exclusively for differences in shallow water, inside the harbor, reproduced variables, in particular tsunami currents.

3.1 Model setup

The computational domain is approximately a square of 7 by 7 km that expands in geographical coordinates in the domain [204.90,204.96] by [19.71,19.773] in longitude and latitude, respectively. Bathymetric data were provided in a lat/lon mesh of 1/3 arcsec resolution (≈ 10 m) in a 692 by 701 point mesh. As mentioned above, this problem has been “reduced” in an attempt to isolate differences in the employed incident wave forcing. For the bathymetry data, this “reduction” is performed as a flattening of the bathymetry at a depth of 30 meters. This means that in the offshore portion of the bathymetry grid there are no depths greater than 30 m (see Figure 1).

Concerning the boundary conditions to be imposed, a time series of offshore simulated free surface elevation at a control point (in white in Figure 1 and located at (19.7576,204.93)) was provided to modelers (Figure 2). The proposed approach was that modelers may force their simulations in whichever way is convenient in order to obtain a modeled time series at the control point as close as possible to the provided data. Note that this represents again a new simplification aiming at reducing model differences up to this point but, in the other hand, this simplification will lead to a physical mismatch between the simulated and the actual data. We chose to impose at the “upper” open boundary the same signal that the one provided for the control point. In Figure 2 upper panel, a comparison between the time series provided at the control point and the numerically simulated with Tsunami-HySEA time series can be found. This simple approach leads to a very good agreement between the two time-series, at least for the four first waves, and quite good qualitative agreement along all the time series. In Figure 2, lower panel, sensitivity to friction for sea surface elevation at this same control point is presented. It is clear that for “deep” waters the influence of the Manning friction coefficient used, within a certain range of values, is minor, and that the magnitude of this coefficient will be mainly feel in very shallow waters and in the inundated coastal strip. Modelers were also encouraged to simulate the

complete problem from the source to the harbor using nesting meshes techniques, being this task optional. Tsunami-HySEA also presented numerical results for the complete scenario as we will show later on.

Fig. 1. Bathymetry data from Hilo Harbor, Hawaii, flattened for depths larger than 30 m. In white the control point, in black the two ADCP locations and in blue the tidal station.

Fig. 2. Control point sea surface time series provided (upper panel in black) compared with Tsunami-HySEA simulated time series (with 1/6 arc sec resolution and Mn=0.03). Lower panel presents sensitivity to the Manning coefficient for Mn = 0.025, 0.03, and 0.035.

3.2 Numerical results for the reduced scenario

To study model convergence, numerical results for three numerical resolutions (2/3, 1/3 and 1/6 arc-sec) were requested. Besides, in order to perform a sensitivity study to friction three values for the Manning coefficient were considered, $n=0.025$ (requested), 0.030 and 0.035 . For the local results in the reduced domain (mandatory), the boundary condition aimed at reproducing the sea surface elevation provided at the control point was set by imposing at the upper grid boundary the same time series provided for the control point.

The first requested comparison consisted in checking the water surface elevation at the tidal station, Hilo Tide Station, located at (19.7308,204.9447) and marked with the blue dot in Figure 1. The comparison of water levels is presented in Figure 3, and shows a reasonable match between the modeled and observed water levels at the harbor gauge. The mismatch for the second wave appears in all models presenting their results during the workshop (NTHMP 2016, Lynett et al 2017) as well as in Zhang et al (2016), independently of their nature (NLSW, Boussinesq or 3D). In Figure 3 lower panel, sensibility of simulated sea surface elevation to friction at the same tide location is presented. Main differences are found at the peaks of the tsunami wave.

Fig. 3. In upper panel, measured data (black line) and numerical simulation (red line, with 1/6 arc sec resolution and $Mn=0.03$) time series of sea surface elevation at the harbor tide gage. Lower panel presents sensitivity to the Manning coefficient for $Mn = 0.025, 0.03, \text{ and } 0.035$.

Then the velocity comparison for the two ADCPs locations provided (marked in black in Figure 1) were required. The official locations of the ADCPs were (could eventually slightly change):

- HA 1125, Harbor Entrance: (19.7452,204.9180)
- HA 1126, Inside Harbor: (19.7417,204.9300)

Figures 4 and 5 show the comparison at these two locations for the u and v components of the velocity currents. In these figures the black dots represent the actual observations. The first clear remark is that frequency sampling for measured data is not short enough to perform a good comparison and precludes a more comprehensive assessment of model results. The actual sampling (6 min) in the measured data is not able to capture the oscillations simulated by the model or to assess if they are real but not captured by sampling, or if they are spurious oscillations produced by

the model. In any case, this is a feature reproduced by many models participating in the workshop, as can be seen in the presentations that can be found at http://coastal.usc.edu/currents_workshop/, regardless the nature of the model (for NLSW, see Tolkova, Nicholsky or Arikawa's presentations; for Boussinesq models Yamazaki or Kirby's and for 3D models Pampell's presentation). In particular, regarding the u-velocity prediction at HA 1125 in Figure 4, we do not know if the model is performing really well or if, by hazard, the red line is always close to the observations marked with the black dots. In any case the agreement for HA 1126 is worse and larger errors are evident. This may be due to the sheltered location of this gauge which made the comparison for all models particularly challenging. It is reassuring how current state of the art numerical models produce qualitatively similar results (NTHMP 2016).

Fig. 4. Measured data (black, dot-dashed line) and numerical simulation (red line, with 1/6 arc sec resolution and $Mn=0.025$) time series of velocity current components (u in upper and v in lower panel) at HA 1125 ADCP.

Fig. 5. Measured data (black, dot-dashed line) and numerical simulation (red line, with 1/6 arc sec resolution and $Mn=0.025$) time series of velocity current components (u in upper and v in lower panel) at HA 1126 ADCP.

For comparison with the figures presented in NTHMP (2016) for all models presenting results for this benchmark problem, we include Figure 6 showing the requested summarizing figure that was required for every model report. This figure presents the comparison for the modulus of the current speed at the two ADCP locations and the free surface elevation at the harbor tide gage. In NTHMP (2016) all model data have been smoothed to produce the analogous figure, as can be observed when comparing for Tsunami-HySEA in page 122 of this report.

Fig. 6. Measured data (black, dashed line) and 1/6 arc sec resolution, $Mn=0.025$ numerical simulation (solid blue line) time series of water elevation at harbor tide gage (top), and current speed modulus at HA25 ADCP (middle), and at HA 1126 ADCP (bottom) locations.

3.2.1 Sensitivity to friction

Regarding sensitivity to friction for current predictions, we observed that it highly depends on the location. Figure 7 shows u and v velocity component comparisons for HA 1125 and HA 1126 ADCP locations. It can be observed how the simulated component velocities at the second location are much more sensitive to varying friction than HA 1125 current predictions. For velocity predictions at HA 1125 differences are only observable at the peaks of the waves, with larger amplitude waves for lower values of friction. In HA 1126 location further differences appear.

Fig. 7. Sensitivity to friction in simulated velocity components at HA 1125 and HA 1126 locations. Comparison with observed data.

3.2.2 Convergence

As mention above, one of the objectives of the present benchmark problem was to assess model convergence with respect to speed predictions as resolution is increased. First, we try to assess convergence comparing the time series at the location where we have measured data. Nevertheless, regarding convergence at punctual discrete locations do not provide much information. The results can be found in Figure 8 for the three mesh resolutions considered. Once again no significant differences are found for HA 1125 ADCP location, at the entrance of the harbor, while for the inside location differences between numerical resolutions are clearly observed.

Fig. 8. Convergence for increased numerical resolution (2/3, 1/3 and 1/6 arcsec) in simulated velocity components at HA 1125 and HA 1126 locations. Comparison with observed data.

To get a two-dimensional picture for convergence in the case of speed predictions, we have considered the modeled maximum fluid speed along all the simulation for the three considered resolutions, 20 m, 10m and 5m, they are shown in Figure 9. To get a better quantifying idea about the difference between the maximum speed predicted for different resolutions, in Figure 10 we present in (a) the difference between the 20m and the 10m resolution simulations, and in panel (b) between the 10m and 5m resolution simulations. It can be observed larger differences for (a) than for (b) which is an indication for convergence (at least of the maximum predicted speed). Nevertheless, strict model simulated speed convergence does not seem to be evident. The presence of eddies makes strict model convergence challenging (Lynett et al 2017), if not impossible if we think at the chaotic nature of the simulated phenomenon (eddies), being matters much easier for the sea surface elevation.

Fig. 9. Maximum predicted fluid speed during entire duration of the (a) 20-m, (b) 10-m and (c) 5-m resolution simulations.

Fig. 10. Maximum predicted fluid speed differences between (a) 20-m and 10-m; (b) 10-m and 5-m resolution simulations.

3.3 Numerical results for the complete scenario

For the **complete scenario** (optional), three nested meshes were used with decreasing resolutions of 128/3, 8/3 arc-sec and for the finer grid the same three resolutions as for the local case were used (2/3, 1/3 and 1/6 arc-sec, corresponding to ≈ 20 , 10, and 5 m respectively). Spatial resolution of outer meshes was also varied to 256/3 and 16/3 in order to assess the role of “ambient” meshes resolution in model results. Two Tohoku 2011 sources, one from NOAA and another from GeoClaw, were used.

3.3 Some comments and conclusions

Some conclusions can be extracted from the numerical results. First for the **reduced scenario**, at HA125 the two initial perturbations in the u and v components of the velocity are well captured, then the simulated u component becomes too oscillatory, but due to the measured data time sampling, it is not possible to confirm if they are spurious numerical oscillations (while present in most of the models participating in the workshop) or if they are real. In general, the effects of varying friction and increasing resolution are very limited, and they are only slightly felt in the maximum and minimum values of the time series (in speed and surface elevation). The observed behavior for HA126 numerical results is similar to the one described for HA125. But, in this case, larger differences are observed for different values of the friction parameter and increased resolution. The differences for the maximum speed maps between the 20m and

5m resolution simulation on the one hand and the 10m minus 5m resolution simulation on the other, suggest convergence of the numerical solution. Hilo TG fit is good.

In what respect the **complete scenario**, simulated from the source, the computed variables reproduce well the first two or three initial waves, in particular for the sea surface elevation in the control point. At HA125 the simulated signal is less oscillatory than in the local scenario and mesh refinement has a minor effect and depending on the sampling (see comments of other modelers), the v component of the speed is well captured or highly overestimated but for the first perturbation. Again, at HA126, larger but still limited sensitivity to mesh refinement is observed. The bad news come when trying to assess sensitivity to the ambient and intermediate mesh resolutions: Much larger sensitivity is now observed, meaning that the “ambient” resolution is important and that the outer meshes can not be very coarse, something we would like to have in order to speedup computations. On the other hand, in Macías et al. (2015) is also shown that going beyond a certain resolution is also useless. All this, while the role of increasing inner resolution remains limited (for the three resolutions considered here). Finally, two different sources were used for the **complete scenario**. Both simulations surprisingly agree quite well, despite the differences in the sources. In general, time series for the velocity components obtained when GeoClaw source is imposed are more oscillatory, mainly for the u component, but both simulations produce good results.

4 Benchmark Problem #3: Tsunami Currents in Tauranga Harbor

This benchmark provides the data for comparison with a field database recording the Japan 2011 tsunami in Tauranga Harbor, New Zealand. Complete details of the dataset provided for this benchmark can be found at http://coastal.usc.edu/currents_workshop/problems/prob3.html and general information about the tsunami impact in New Zealand can be found in Borrero et al. (2013). During the 2011 Tohoku Tsunami at Tauranga Harbor in the Bay of Plenty and home to the Port of Tauranga, several sea water level and current speed data were recorded. They summed up a total of 5 water level gauges (TAUT, Moturiki, A Beacon, Tug Berth and Sulfur Point) and one ADCP measuring current speed in the entrance of the harbor (their locations can be found at Figure 1). This represents one of the most comprehensive instrumental data set of a far-field tsunami affecting a major commercial port. Besides, at the ADCP measurement location, the speed component of the tsunami signal is comparable to the tidal component, indicating the possibility of a non-linear superposition of the two components. The aim of this test is to attempt to include the effects of the tides in the tsunami model simulations.

Fig. x1. Location map showing the entrance to Tauranga Harbor and locations of the water level and current meters

4.1 Model setup

The numerical model setup used for the simulations presented here is exactly the same as the one proposed in the benchmark description. A rotated domain of 40 km by 20 km with a 20-meter numerical resolution was used, resulting in a 2 million-cell size problem (bathymetry data resolution 10 m, shown in Figure x2). The computational domain was rotated in order to make it easier to impose the boundary condition along the “upper” domain boundary in Figure x2. Modelers were asked to drive their simulations with the most offshore measured free surface elevation (at A Beacon tide gage). This tide gage is located at a 25-meter depth. Three separate time series at this location were provided: 1) only tide, 2) only tsunami and 3) the combined tide+tsunami signals. Depending on the simulated scenario modelers should choose among these forcing signals. We performed simulations for the three cases.

Fig. x2. Bathymetric data provided in the 40 by 20 km computational domain.

4.2 Numerical results

The numerical results show a good agreement with measured data both for free surface elevation at the four tidal stations and for the three different configurations (tide only, tsunami only and tide plus tsunami signal). In the present benchmark problem, comparison with free surface elevation data was performed at four tidal stations, named and location in geographical and as the x-y coordinate system of the rotated bathymetry data is collected in Table 1 and their locations are shown in Figure x1.

	latitude	longitude	x	y
A Beacon	-37.60287	176.17781	2.724e4	1.846e4
Tur Berth	-37.6407	176.1809	3.085e4	1.512e4
Sulfur Point	-37.6596	176.1755	3.2e4	1.347e4
Moturiki	-37.6307	176.18377	3.005e4	1.61e4
ADCP	-37.6416	176.1653	2.925e4	1.466e4

Table x1. Geographical coordinates and x-y coordinate system of the rotated bathymetry data of the four tidal stations and the official location of the ADCP.

4.2.1 Sea surface elevation

In Figure x3, measured vs simulated tsunami-only signal at the four tidal stations is shown. Very good agreement can be observed between both time series at the four locations. Figurex5 shows the same comparison but for the tsunami plus tide signal. For the sake of completeness, we also present the comparison for the only tide time series (Figure x6), as suggested in the benchmark instructions.

Fig. x3. Comparison of the free surface elevation at the 4 tidal stations for tsunami-only signal.

Fig. x4. Comparison of the free surface elevation at the 4 tidal stations for tsunami plus tide signal.

Fig. x5. Comparison of the free surface elevation at the 4 tidal stations for the only tide signal.

4.2.2 Tsunami currents

In this section, we compare the numerical results with the measured ADCP speed data. In Figure xx the modulus for the measured speed is presented in blue, then the filtered tsunami and tidal signal are also shown in red and black, respectively. Maximum measured current speed during the tsunami reached 2.5 m/s in the entrance of Tauranga Harbor. Removing the tidal component shows that the tsunami currents alone peak at approximately 1.0 m/s. In Figure

xx the green line represents the threshold for the passage of large container ships through the entrance to Tauranga Harbor (Borrero et al, 2015).

Fig. x2. Measured current during the 2011 Tohoku tsunami. Total measured current in red, filtered tidal signal in red and filtered tidal signal in blank. Green line represents the 0.77 m/s threshold for large ships navigation.

Figure x7 depicts the comparison between depth-average horizontal velocity data at ADCP location and simulated depth-average velocity, showing numerical results good agreement with observed data. It must be noted

Fig. x5. Depth average horizontal velocity comparison Tsunami-HySEA model-ADCP data for the only tide experiment (a), only tsunami (b), and complete experiment.

4.2.3 Some comments

5 Final conclusions

The overall conclusion that we could extract from this validation exercise was that the Tsunami-HySEA model performed well in all benchmark problems proposed, being the most difficult one the first benchmark. For BP2 -Hilo Harbor- good agreement is obtained for the control point and the tidal station for sea surface elevation. Depth average velocities show a good fit for the initial pattern of the signal (in u and v), becoming noisier for the u component at location HA1125 (see comments of other modelers on data sampling for this case). We analyzed sensitivity to friction

and convergence when mesh is refined. Differences in maximum velocity between 20m, 10m and 5m mesh resolutions suggest model convergence. The simulation of the complete scenario from the source in the whole Pacific domain was also performed, obtaining also in this case a good fit for sea surface elevation signals at control point and at Hilo tide station. For the velocity time series, a good agreement of the initial phase of the signal and less oscillatory time series for the u component is obtained in this case. Sensitivity to mesh refinement showed minor effects for inner finer meshes and larger effects for the outer coarser ambient meshes. BP3 –Tauranga Harbor- was performed in the three requested configurations (only tsunami, tsunami+tide and only tide). The time series for these three configurations for the sea surface elevation at the four locations considered is very good and also a very good fit is obtained for the speed signal at the ACDP location.

As Tsunami-HySEA is composed of a family of numerical schemes, well adapted to different flow configurations, in general it has produced good results in all the benchmark problems without the need of any new implementation. The sole exception was for BP1, which we found the more difficult one, mainly due to the simplicity of the shallow water model that we used for this test. We think that a better parameterization of the viscous effects should be included in the model in order to obtain a good fit with experimental data. For the rest of the BPs, the use of Tsunami-HySEA was simple and straightforward. Besides, for the very first time we tested a dispersive version of the model and applied to BP5. For large scale, highly computationally demanding problems (as BP2, complete scenario), Tsunami-HySEA performs extremely fast, producing accurate simulations in very short computational times. For such problems nested meshes were used.

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